

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SNOW****FIRST NAME: ROMILLA****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 9%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Kate Turabian begins her manual with a definition of research. She states that a student's attitude and positive thinking
- Will help him or her write the research proposal faster.
 - Will help him or her overcome a sometimes tedious process.¹**
 - Makes the research hypothesis have integrity.
 - Will not matter if the research sources are cited correctly.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and the University of Chicago Editorial Staff, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 5-8.

2. The EUCLID ACA-401D course packet encourages students to focus upon the research question while reading journal articles to use a sources. This is because the research question

- Is the main or controlling idea of the dissertation.²**
- Can be put aside until the methodology section is complete.
- Need not be the central topic, as this is too simplistic.
- Should be overlooked when writing a clear argument.

3. Kate Turabian teaches students how to craft arguments in a logical fashion. She warns students to create arguments that are not just a “patchwork of sources” because

- The student will be seen as an amateur and plagiarist.³**
- The patchwork of sources is only used in the conclusion section.
- Logical arguments are easier to craft with many opposing arguments .
- Convincing arguments are not logical.

4. When student’s read the guide by Bloomberg and Volpe, why does it say they only teach dissertation structure?

- Bloomberg and Volpe are not qualified to teach other subjects.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 11.

³ Turabian, 67.

- The student needs to speculate creatively while staying within the traditional dissertation structure.⁴**
- Their guide says most doctoral students have little maturity or confidence.
- Each student needs to consult several professors for the whole framework.
5. Bloomberg and Volpe say most students choose a qualitative research approach over a quantitative research approach. Why is this?
- The qualitative approach uses too many numbers, facts, and statistics.
- The quantitative research approach is best for social problems and case studies.
- It is not necessary to choose either approach; just make sound arguments.
- Most students choose a qualitative approach expecting a more free and exploratory experience while they investigate a research problem.⁵**
6. Turabian explains that a good scholar uses research sources to contradict his or her research hypothesis. What is the reason these contradictory sources are used?
- The student did not research enough supporting evidence to fill the reference section.
- Dissertations introducing contradictory studies present the full scope of the research problem.⁶**
- Students create weak arguments when they present opposing research claims.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications, 2019), 34-35.

⁵ Ibid., 7-8.

⁶ Turabian, 140.

- Opposing arguments may be more interesting than the original hypothesis.
7. According to the European Commission style guide, why do writers use hyphens?
- Hyphens are used for pronouns and capitalized nouns.
- The writer can choose not to hyphenate.
- Writers use hyphens to create new words that are not in the dictionary.
- The rule is to hyphenate two words that act as an adjective for a noun.**⁷
8. The European Commission warns employees, workers, and other staff that using “in-house jargon” in documents is unacceptable. What is “in-house jargon”?
- These are words the European Union says are not inclusive pronouns.
- The documents should include slang and other specialized European Union vocabulary.
- These are words or terms inherent to each European Union agency that the general public does not understand.**⁸
- Jargon means terminology. Jargon is a way to speak in plain, easily understood language.
9. The European Commission says that when documents are written in a multilingual environment, common words are formed from a language “interference effect”. What are the two most common languages in the European Union?⁹

⁷ The European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (Luxembourg: European Union, 2021), 20-24.

⁸ Ibid., 22.

⁹ Ibid., 19.

- British, United Kingdom English and American English
- English and German
- The idea that there are only two most common languages in the EU is not inclusive.
- English and French**

10. Why does EUCLID require all doctorate students take ACA-401D?

- There was a general consensus among EUCLID professors that Dr. Gulma needed to have more work.
- It created this class to “level the playing field” for international scholarship within EUCLID programs. ¹⁰**
- EUCLID ensures student retention and student interest in EUCLID doctorate programs by offering international writing.
- It does not require all doctorate students to take international writing.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 7.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.